

Synthesis of 1-Dioxides of 2-Aryl-3-benzyl-4-thiazolidones

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Surrey and Cutler (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 578) prepared 1-dioxides of 2-halophenyl-4-thiazolidones and found them to possess amoebicidal activity. Several 2-aryl-3-benzyl-4-thiazolidones, prepared in this laboratory (Raval and Trivedi, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 353), have been oxidised by potassium permanganate to the corresponding 1-dioxides.

Procedure.—The 1-dioxides were prepared as follows. A solution of KMnO_4 (0.65 g.) in water (15 c.c.) was added with stirring to a solution of 2-aryl-3-benzyl-4-thiazolidones (0.002*M*) in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) at 35–40°. Stirring was continued for about 30 minutes. A sodium bisulphite solution was added to remove the excess of KMnO_4 and the 1-dioxides were separated on adding water with continuous stirring. 1-Dioxides (yield about 50%) were crystallised from ethanol. The compounds obtained are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	R.	R'.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	116°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{NClS}$	9.7	9.5
2.	H	3,4-Di-Me	134°	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{NS}$	9.8	9.7
3.	H	<i>p</i> -OMe	184°	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{NS}$	9.9	9.7
4.	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	136°	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}_2\text{S}$	8.9	8.7
5.	<i>p</i> -OMe	2,4-Di-Me	160°	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2\text{NS}$	9.1	8.9

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